

STUDIES IN CATALYTIC REACTIONS OF CHARCOAL. PART II. CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF HYDROGEN PEROXIDE

BALWANT RAI PURI, LEKH RAJ SHARMA AND D. D. SINGH

The catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solutions of different concentrations by sugar charcoal, original as well as degassed at 750° and at 1200°, has been studied in some details. The activity is found to be minimum in the case of the original sample and maximum in the case of the sample degassed at 120°. The difference in the activity of the samples, prepared from the same material, can be attributed to the nature of their surface, acidic in the former and alkaline in the latter. The degassed sample chemisorbs an appreciable amount of oxygen in the course of the reaction, leading to the formation of a surface-oxygen complex, capable of evolving CO₂ on high temperature evacuation. This complex renders the charcoal surface acidic and considerably lowers its activity for the reaction. A reasonable mechanism for the reaction has been suggested.

It is well known that hydrogen peroxide undergoes catalytic decomposition at the surfaces of dispersed solids. It is generally believed that large surface of these substances is responsible for their catalytic activity. Activated charcoal is also known to be an effective catalyst for the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide (Firth and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1750; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 20, 370; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 987; Skumburdis, *Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 55, 156; King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1688). King (*loc. cit.*) and Larsen and Walton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, 45, 476) have shown that the catalytic activity of charcoal depends upon the temperature of its activation, being maximum at 850° and minimum at 400°. Since the samples activated at 850° and 400° differ markedly in their p_H values (King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 889) as well as acid-base adsorption capacity (Puri *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1953, 60, 1071), it appears that the nature of the surface rather than its magnitude plays an important role in bringing about the reaction. The perusal of the literature shows that the mechanism of this reaction is not properly understood and several conflicting views have been put forward, amongst others by King (*loc. cit.*, 1936), Brinkmann (*Angew. Chem.*, 1949, 61, 373; *Kolloid Z.*, 1951, 123, 116) and Garten and Weiss (*Aust. J. Appl. Sci.*, 1956, 7, 145).

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoal samples.—Three samples of sugar charcoal, viz., (i) original, (ii) degassed at 750° and (iii) degassed at 1200°, as described in Part I (this *issue*, p. 765), were used in these experiments as well. Their surface areas, as calculated from water adsorption isotherms, were found to be 480, 491 and 486 sq. in/g. respectively.

Procedure.—The charcoal sample (1 g. portion each) was mixed with 100 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide solutions of different concentrations and the suspension shaken mechanically for 24 hours after which an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was titrated against a standard potassium permanganate solution. A blank was also run simultaneously in every case.

The results of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide solutions of different concentrations by the various samples of sugar charcoal are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ solns. of diff. conc. by the various samples of sugar charcoal.

Conc. of soln.	H ₂ O ₂ added.	Amount decomp. (Blank).	H ₂ O ₂ decomposed in the Original.	presence of charcoal Degassed at 750°.	Degassed at 1200°.
0.10 N	10.0 m.e.	0.50 m.e.	0.50 m.e.	2.15 m.e.	5.00 m.e.
0.50	50.0	1.80	1.90	3.50	9.40
0.75	75.0	2.01	2.00	3.65	10.50
1.00	100.0	2.60	2.75	4.50	11.15
1.50	150.0	2.83	2.90	6.80	12.20
1.71	171.0	3.00	3.21	8.10	17.00
2.40	240.0	5.00	5.50	9.00	21.50
2.81	281.0	6.50	7.10	9.65	22.50
3.54	354.0	7.50	7.90	10.50	23.82
4.00	400.0	8.50	9.01	13.65	25.00

DISCUSSION

It is seen that the original sample has very little catalytic activity, the amount decomposed being only slightly larger than that decomposed in the absence of any foreign material. The evacuated samples, on the other hand, bring about the reaction to appreciable extents, the magnitude increasing with increase in the concentration of the peroxide solution.

Now since the original sample gave acid reactions in aqueous suspension (p_H 2.85) and those degassed at 750° and 1200° gave alkaline reactions (p_H 7.20 and 8.78 respectively), it appears that alkaline surface is far more conducive to catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide than the acidic surface. Also, since all the three samples have nearly the same surface area, as already mentioned, it is evident that the nature, and not the magnitude of the surface, is of primary importance in bringing about this reaction.

Hydrogen peroxide, though an extremely weak acid, dissociates slightly as :

and has a dissociation constant equal to 2.4×10^{-12} . It appears therefore quite probable that when hydrogen peroxide is brought in contact with the alkaline surface of the degassed charcoal, the first step in its decomposition lies in the adsorption of H⁺ ions at the charcoal surface. This view receives support from the observations of Steenberg ("Adsorption and Exchange of Ions on Activated Charcoal", 1944, Almquist and Wiksells, Uppsala) that such charcoals can take up H⁺ ions by primary adsorption from acid solution and that the acid anions are held next to hydrogen ions by electrostatic effect. Thus the OOH⁻ ions are held next to H⁺ ions along the charcoal surface. Now the

OOH⁻ ions, being even less stable than the peroxide itself, decompose, liberating oxygen as represented below :

The H⁺ and OH⁻ ions may unite to form unionised water. This leaves the charcoal surface again in a position to take up more H⁺ ions (unless it undergoes a fundamental change in its nature in the mean while, as discussed later, *vide infra*) and the dissociation and decomposition of hydrogen peroxide progress further.

It would be of interest to know the manner in which the oxygen given out by hydrogen peroxide in the presence of charcoal is disposed of. There are three possibilities: it might appear as free oxygen; it might oxidise some of the carbon to carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide, and finally it might be chemisorbed by the carbon, giving rise to surface-oxygen complexes. All the three possibilities were tested. For the first two, the gaseous mixture above the solution in each reaction bottle was sampled and analysed for its oxygen, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide contents in the Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus. The values were corrected for the amounts of these gases normally present in air, as determined by a similar analysis of the air in the room. For the third possibility, the charcoal left after the reaction was washed thoroughly with distilled water, dried and evacuated at 1200°. The gases evolved were analysed for CO, CO₂ and H₂O in the usual way. The results are shown in Tables II and III. It may be mentioned that no free carbon monoxide or carbon dioxide (in excess of the normal amount) was found above the reaction solution in any of the experiments, thus ruling out the second possibility altogether.

TABLE II

Decomposition of H₂O₂ by charcoal degassed at 750° and the amount of oxygen rendered available.

[O₂ evolved as CO₂ on evacuating the treated samples at 1200° (II) = Nil].

Conc. of soln.	Amount decomposed with charcoal.	Free O ₂ collected in the bottle. (I).	Total oxygen. (I+II).	p _H of aq. suspension of charcoal.
0.10 N	2.15 m.e.	2.20 m.e.	2.20 m.e.	7.20
0.50	3.50	3.44	3.44	7.21
0.75	3.65	3.70	3.70	6.99
1.00	4.50	4.40	4.40	7.18
1.50	6.80	6.71	6.71	7.05
1.71	8.10	7.99	7.99	7.10
2.40	9.00	8.89	8.89	6.98
2.81	9.65	9.72	9.72	7.13
3.54	10.50	10.43	10.43	6.97
4.00	13.65	13.40	13.40	7.23

TABLE III

Decomposition of H_2O_2 by charcoal degassed at 1200° and the account of oxygen rendered available.

Conc. of soln.	Amount decomposed with charcoal.	Free O_2 collected in the bottle. (I).	O_2 evolved as CO_2 on evacuating the treated samples at 1200° . (II).	Total oxygen. (I+II).	p_H of aq. suspension of charcoal.	Amount of H_2O_2 decomposed by charcoal sample already treated with $4N-H_2O_2$.
0.10 N	5.00 m.e.	3.43 m.e.	1.51 m.e.	4.94 m.e.	8.78	
0.50	9.40	6.68	2.66	9.34	8.67	
0.75	10.50	6.97	3.48	10.45	7.80	
1.00	11.15	7.26	3.71	10.97	7.66	3.15 m.e.
1.50	12.00	7.88	4.00	11.88	7.12	3.41
1.71	17.00	11.02	5.98	17.00	6.78	
2.40	21.50	12.00	9.98	21.98	5.17	7.46
2.81	22.50	13.84	8.73	22.57	5.10	9.00
3.54	23.82	14.92	8.75	23.67	5.10	
4.00	25.00	16.38	9.15	25.53	5.12	11.15

It is evident that in the case of the reactions with the sample degassed at 750° (Table II), all the oxygen rendered available from the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide is evolved as elementary gas and that none of it is chemisorbed. There is consequently no change in the nature of the surface, the p_H value of charcoal remaining the same. However, in the reactions with the sample degassed at 1200° (Table III), some of the oxygen is evolved as elementary gas and the rest is chemisorbed by the charcoal. The latter is recovered entirely as CO_2 and not at all as CO or H_2O on subsequent evacuation at 1200° . It is interesting to note that the entire amount of oxygen resulting from the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide at each concentration is completely accounted for, partly as free oxygen and partly as chemisorbed oxygen. The latter, however, acquires a constant value after an appreciable decomposition has taken place and any oxygen rendered available thereafter is evolved as free gas. This shows incidentally that charcoal has only a limited capacity to chemisorb oxygen.

The presence of the oxygen complex capable of evolving CO_2 is known to render the charcoal surface acidic (Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 357). The p_H values of the aqueous suspensions of the residual charcoals left after the reaction were determined (Table III). It is seen that there is a progressive decrease in the p_H value of the charcoal, showing clearly that the charcoal undergoes distinct surface alterations (from basic to acidic character) in the course of the reaction.

Now, as acid surface cannot be so effective in bringing about the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide, the degassed charcoal should ultimately tend to lose its activity for this reaction. This was verified by working with the residual sample left after treatment with $4N$ solution of hydrogen peroxide and having p_H 5.12. The amounts of hydrogen

peroxide decomposed by it were now found to be extremely small (Table III, last column) and only slightly greater than the amounts decomposed in blank experiments (Table I).

In conclusion, it may be mentioned that the observations recorded in this paper can neither be explained satisfactorily by the reaction mechanism proposed by Brinkmann (*loc. cit.*) as it does not account for chemisorption of oxygen by charcoal and subsequent alterations in its surface characteristics nor by that, proposed by Garten and Weiss (*loc. cit.*) which, while providing for chemisorption of oxygen and surface alterations, cannot explain the removal of the entire amount of chemisorbed oxygen as carbon dioxide, which is actually the case. Moreover, the surface groups postulated by them cannot remain intact on degassing carbons at 1200°. The mechanism proposed in the paper, on the other hand, appears to explain all the observed facts.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
HOSHIARPUR.

Received July 21, 1958.